

Experimental constraints on the behaviour of heat-producing elements in highly reduced planetary mantles.

Table 1. Proposed high-pressure experimental runs designed to investigate HPE partitioning in reduced aubrite-like mantle compositions.

Run	Pressure	Temperature	Composition	Purpose
EXP-1	1 GPa	1400 °C	AUB + Fe-Si	baseline partitioning
EXP-2	2.5 GPa	1600 °C	AUB + Fe-Si	pressure effect
EXP-3	2.5 GPa	1600 °C	AUB + Fe-Si + S	sulfur influence
EXP-4	1 GPa	1400 °C	AUB + Fe-Si	replicate run to test equilibrium
EXP-5	2.5 GPa	1600 °C	AUB + Fe-Si + S	replicate run for sulfur experiment

Figure 1. Workflow of the proposed Transnational Access project, including preparation of starting materials, high-pressure experiments at PISL (VU Amsterdam), recovery of experimental products, and initial SEM characterization during the TA visit. Detailed compositional and trace element analyses (EPMA and LA-ICP-MS) will be performed after the TA visit.

References

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